

A COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF AGE AND SEX RELATED VARIATIONS IN HEMATOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN LASSI BREED CAMELS (CAMELUS DROMEDARIUS)

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Abstract

Background: Camels play pivotal role in in dessert areas, especially in Pakistan, where the Lassi breed is common. To keep camels healthy and productive, it's important to understand their blood and body functions. **Objective:** To evaluate the influence of age and sex on hematological and physiological parameters in Lassi camels breed. **Methodology:** This study was carried out on sixty humped males and female lassi breed (*Camelus dromedarius*) aged between 3 months to 72 months in Lasbela district, Balochistan. Animals were divided into 6 groups placing 10 animals in each group: Group A: 3-24 months' male, Group B: 3-24 month's female camels, Group C: 25-48 months' male camels and Group D: 25-48 months' female camels, Group E: 60-72 months' male camels, Group F: 60-72 months' female camels. All the camels were clinically healthy and free from any physical abnormalities. **Results:** Group-F had the highest recorded rectal temperature (101.96 ± 0.21 OF), whereas group-A had the lowest recorded temperature (100.79 ± 0.18 OF). Group-D had the highest heart rate (26.00 ± 0.89 beats per minute), whereas group-A had the lowest heart rate (25.20 ± 0.86 beats per minute). Group-F had the highest respiratory rate (10.40 ± 0.24 breaths per minute), whereas group-A had the lowest (6.20 ± 0.58 breaths per minute). Group-F received the highest RBC count ($10.40 \pm 0.24 \times 10^6 / \mu\text{L}$), whereas group-A received the lowest ($6.80 \pm 0.37 \times 10^6 / \mu\text{L}$). Group-F showed the highest PCV count ($43.60 \pm 0.33\%$), whereas group-A showed the lowest ($32.40 \pm 1.12\%$). Group-F had the highest hemoglobin count (15.40 ± 0.40 g/dl), whereas group-A had the lowest number (11.20 ± 0.37 g/dl). Group-F had the highest MCV count (34.00 ± 0.89 fL), whereas group-A had the lowest (26.20 ± 0.37 fL). Group-A had the lowest MCH count (17.00 ± 0.14 fL), whereas Group-F had the highest number (32.31 ± 0.06 fL). Among the groups, Group-F had the highest MCHC count

(51.50±0.47 g/dl) while group-A had the lowest (43.40±0.92 g/dl). Group-F showed the highest neutrophil count (36.10±0.37×10³ uL), whereas group-A showed the lowest (27.90±0.23 ×10³ uL). Eosinophil counts ranged from a low of 6.14±0.01×10³ uL in group-A to a maximum of 8.38±0.27 ×10³ uL in Group-F. Group-F had the highest basophil count (1.52±0.09 ×10³ uL), whereas group-A exhibited the lowest (1.16±0.06 ×10³ uL%). Group-F had the highest lymphocyte count measured at 53.10±0.45 ×10³ uL, while group-A had the lowest at 43.40±0.40 ×10³ uL. Monocyte counts ranged from a low of 5.32±0.05 ×10³ uL in group-A to a high of 7.34±0.07 ×10³ uL in Group-F.

Conclusions: It was revealed that Lassi male adult camels had numerically higher values for the majority of the physiological and hematological markers than did other age groups. Compared to other age groups, Lassi foal male camels had lower blood parameter values.

INTRODUCTION

Camel is a one of the ruminant animals that is well adapted to the harsh environment of desert and is used for transportation, racing, and considered as a source of meat, milk and wool (1). Worldwide, there are nearly 28 million camels, 24 million of which are in Africa, 4 million in Asia and just 7,000 in Europe. About 94% of the estimated world camel population is single-humped or dromedary camels, while the remaining 6% are two-humped Bactrian camels in Asia. (2).

Total population of camels in Pakistan is 1.160 million in the world, after Somalia, Sudan and India. Camels are used in many purposes such as meat production and carnal labor. They mainly contribute to the farming system, which have affected dry drought patients, where they provide the main source of minerals based on the income of the villagers. The documented various breeds of Pakistan, camel breed belong to Sindh are such as Larri, Kharai, Sakrai and Dhatti. Camel breed belong to Balochistan are Kachhi, Brahvi, Makrani, Lassi, Rodbari, Pisin and Kharani from Baluchistan, camel breed belong to Punjab are Marecha Bagri, Brela and Campbelpuri, camel breeds belong to Khyber Pashtunkhwa are Kala-Chitta, Ghuimani, Gaddi, Khader and Maya, Bacterian (double-humped) from Northern areas of Pakistan (3). The dromedarius is also called single humped camel that was domesticated 5,000 years ago (3,000 years B.C.) in the Arabian Peninsula. The name dromedary is derived from dromos means road in Greek due to in relation with use of camel in transportation. The

family camelidae is divided in to classes, llama and Camelus. The class camelus includes two type, Camelus dromedaries, single-humped and camelus Bactrianus, double- humped camel. The class llama includes four species, llama glama, llama pacos, Alpaca which are domesticated and llama guanaco (4).

The camel is a domesticated animal in most deserted countries area of the world. It has ability to adapt the hard climatic condition such as extremely high environmental temperature of arid zones of Asia and Africa (5). Because of high ability of Camel to sustain hardships of desertification in Jordan many of pastoralists in Northern Kordofan and Darfour replaced camel farming (6). Camels are an excellent source of high quality animal protein, it can produce good amount of meat even in adverse climatic conditions due to great tolerance to high temperatures, solar radiation, water scarcity, rough topography and poor vegetation (7). Camel milk has potential medicinal and therapeutic properties, such as anti-diabetic (8), anti-carcinogenic (9), anti-hypertensive (10) and it is useful for treatment of immunity deficiencies disease such as AIDS (11).

Camel provides meat, milk and wool to the rural society and also used for transport goods and crops. Camels in some countries took part in the national economy; camel racing in Arab countries for some time has made new and additional proportion in the camel industry. West and East Sudan have made camel a major source of economy in those parts of the country to spread camel performance in arid and

semi-arid areas. (12). Animals' performance is bear by interaction between genotype and environment. Their physical attributes are the convenient types of domestic lovers that are used in extreme arid condition. All the functions of the camel organism are conceived to be physiologically adapted to "water and food restrictions" and also to a very hot climate (13). High temperature greatly affects the fertility and production rate in domestic animals (14). Temperature has also great impact on the concentration of milk and blood enzymes and compositions well in animals (15). Camel physiology features are challenge to interested research workers, temperature, respiratory and heart rates are used as an environmental stress indicator. It is rapidly realized that most of the essential information about hemogram, blood metabolite and hormone in camels plays a very important role in understanding the physiology of the species (16).

Blood constituent tests may offer useful benefits and indicators about the overall welfare of livestock. A sign for diagnosis or differential diagnosis of a diseased condition may be the detection of a divergence of certain blood parameters from their normal limits (17, 18). Hematology is an important method in veterinary medicine for diagnosis and treatment. The blood image offers an incentive to scientifically examine the existence in the animal's body of multiple metabolites and other elements and plays a lustrous function in the determination of an organism's physiological, dietary and pathological status (19). It seems to be important to compare blood values under various management schemes, since these values can represent the animal's well-being and could be used as diagnostic tools for animal disease and health (20, 21, 22). (23), during the dry season, the number of red blood cells, lymphocytes and basophiles increased significantly, whereas the proportion of MCV, MCH and neutrophils increased significantly during the green season. (24, 25, 26, 27) on indigenous chickens, published a report. They recorded that the influence of the age group on PCV, RBC and WBC was observed, where the 150th age group reported the highest WBC, PCV; higher RBC values were observed for the 90d age group. For the WBC, the age group of 90 was the largest. There was also a major sex influence, with males having higher PCV

and RBC values and females exhibiting greater WBC value. For MCV and MCHC, a major age effect was found. With females having the highest value on MCHC, major sex influence was visible whereas males had higher MCV. A research performed by (28, 29, 30) on haematological parameters of rabbit breeds and crosses in humid tropics reported genotype effect on PCV, WBC, MCH and ESR; values of RBC, HBC and MCHC were equivalent in all genotypes, leading to comparable cellular haemoglobin content in the blood samples collected. The disease of Camel surra is one of the most severe diseases in camels, causing many economic losses. The typical characteristics of trypanosomiasis in camels are anemia and leukocytosis (31). As previously stated in the analysis the lower haematological values of RBCs, Hb concentration, PCV percent were considered as an indicator of anemia (32) In the sub-clinically contaminated camels in the sample, the lower PCV percentage and RBCs count values were consistent with prior findings reduction in MCV values regarded as an indication of erythrophagocytosis (33). (34) also stated that the extreme anemia was due to depression of erythropoiesis, which may be a result of chronic inflammation of the camel's liver. In addition, there was a strong association between the infestation level and the numbers of RBCs, PCV percentage and Hb concentration levels. During trypanosomiasis, leukocytosis may be a result of increased activation of the mononuclear phagocytic system (35). A substantial increase in mean TLC and lymphocyte values in trypanosoma infected camels relative to non-infected camels during the original, mid and late breeding seasons was observed in the study. This finding was close to the findings stated by (31) in numerous fields. This increase in TLC (total leukocyte count) was in line with (33) that attributed the increase in cell-mediated response to the infection fighting increase. In response to physiological health factors, blood constituents alter (36). According to (37), changes in hematological parameters are often used to determine various status of the body and determine stresses due to environmental, nutritional and/or pathological factors. Increasing in blood and milk serum enzymes indicate the liver's abnormality (15).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried out on sixty humped male and female lassi breed (*Camelus dromedarius*) aged between 3 months to 72 months. Animals were divided into 6 groups placing 10 animals in each group: Group A: 3-24 months' male foal, Group B: 3-24 month's female foal camels, Group C: 25-48 months' male adult camels and Group D: 25-48 months' female adult camels, Group E: 60-72 months' male young camels, Group F: 60-72 months' female young camels. All the camels were clinically healthy and free from any physical abnormalities.

Table 1: Experimental design

Age (months)	Male	Female
3-24	G-A (foal)#10	G-B (foal)#10
25-48	G-C (young)#10	G-D (young)#10
60-72	G-E (adult)#10	G-F (adult)#10

Blood collection

Blood samples (10 ml) were collected from jugular vein using (10 ml) plastic disposable syringes and (4 ml) vacuainers' tube with gel. Blood was taken from jugular vein puncture by the disposable syringe. Immediately (3 ml) of the blood were delivered into tube containing EDTA as an anticoagulant for the hematological analyses. The blood was used for determining the normal values of PCV, MCV, MCH, MCHC, Hb, and the remainder of the samples which were kept into plain plastic tubes allowed clotting for 2h at room temperature; the sera were then separated by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 15 min and stored in sealed plastic containers at -20 °C until analyzed. Differential leukocyte count (DLC) was determined microscopically from a count of 100 leukocytes in thin May-Giemsa stained blood smears Hematology-analyzer.

Clinical parameters

Rectal temperatures (Tr)

The rectal temperature (Tr) of the camel was measured by using a digital thermometer. The thermometer was disinfected. The animals were handled gently and the probe was inserted into the rectum 5cm touching the wall of the rectum for two minutes in morning at 8:00 am and also at 4:00 pm in evening.

Respiration rate (RR)

The respiration rate (RR) was obtained by using stethoscope counting the frequency of lung movement per minute using a stopwatch in morning at 8:00 am and also at 4:00 pm in evening.

Heart rate

The heart rate was determined by counting the frequency of the heart beats with stethoscope per minute using a stopwatch. Heart rate was recorded in morning at 8:00 am and also at 4:00 pm in evening.

Blood analysis

Hematological values

The methods described by Jain (1998) were used for determination of, packed cell volume (PCV), hemoglobin concentration (Hb), and differential leukocyte count (DLC). The erythrocytic indices, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), were calculated according to formulae of Jain (1998) and also use the Hematology-analyzer for the calculation of normal values of blood constituents.

Erythrocyte count

Red blood cells were determined by diluting blood sample with physiological solution (Hayem's solution), and counting the number of RBCs using an improved Neubaur haematocytometer (Neubaur improve - Germany) (Jain, 1998).

Packed cell volume (PCV)

Capillary tubes were used for measuring packed cell volume; tubes were filled with blood above 3/4 and sealed with crista seal, then were centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 5 minutes by a micro-haemotocrit centrifuge (Hettich, Tuttlingen - Germany). Haemotocrit reader was used for determines the percentage of PCV (Jain, 1998) and also used Hematology-analyzer to determine the normal %PCV.

Hemoglobin concentration (Hb)

Spin react Hemoglobin Drabkin kit (SPINREACT, Spin) was used for determining hemoglobin concentration using colorimetric method and also

Used Hematology-analyzer to determine the normal %Hb

Mean corpuscular volume (MCV)

The %MCV, in femtoliters (fl) was calculated from the blood by Jain formula and Hematology-analyzer machine.

Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH)

The % of MCH, in picogram (Pg) was calculated from blood by Jain formula using Hematology-analyzer machine.

Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC)

The %MCHC, in (g/dl) was calculated from blood by Jain formula by using Hematology-analyzer machine.

Differential leukocyte count (DLC)

Neutrophils, eosinophils, basophils, lymphocytes and monocytes were determined by the microscope from a count of leukocytes in thin smears using the procedure of scientist (38) and also used Hematology-analyzer to determine the normal % of DLC for proper result.

RESULTS

Temperature (°F) of Lassi Camel

Table 2 indicates that maximum rectal temperature was recorded in Group-F, 101.96±0.21 °F and the minimum rectal temperature was observed in group- A, 101.32±0.24 °F.

Table 2: Rectal Temperature (°F) of Lassi camel

Animals	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	100.2	101.8	100.2	100.8	101.4	102.8
2	101.8	101.6	100.5	100.6	101.8	101.6
3	100.4	101.8	100.8	101.2	102.2	102.8
4	101.6	100.4	100.3	100.8	101.6	102.4
5	100.3	100.8	101.8	100.6	101.4	101.2
6	101.3	100.2	101.2	100.8	101.3	101.8
7	100.8	101.6	101.9	100.6	101.8	101.6
8	100.4	102.8	101.8	101.6	102.2	102.8
9	100.6	101.4	101.9	101.8	101.6	101.4
10	100.5	100.8	100.8	100.6	101.4	101.2
Mean ±SE	100.79 ±0.18	101.32 ±0.24	101.12 ±0.21	100.94 ±0.14	101.67 ±0.10	101.96 ±0.21

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant (p<0.05) difference between them

Heart rate (beat/min)

Table 3 displays that maximum heart rate was recorded in group- D, 26.00 ±0.89 beat/min and the minimum heart rate were observed same in both group-A and Group-E, 25.40±0.50 beat/min.

Table 3: Heart rate (beat/min) of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	26	25	27	29	28	25
2	28	27	28	27	26	24
3	24	25	24	24	25	23
4	25	26	25	25	24	28
5	23	24	25	25	23	29
6	26	25	27	29	28	25
7	28	27	28	27	26	24
8	24	25	24	24	25	23
9	25	26	25	25	24	28
10	23	24	25	25	23	29
Mean ± SE	25.20 ±0.86b	25.40 ±0.50b	25.80 ±0.73b	26.00 ±0.89a	25.20 ±0.86b	25.50 ±1.15b

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between them

Respiratory rate (breath/min) of Lassi Camel

Table 4 reveals that maximum respiratory rate was recorded in Group-F, 10.40 ± 0.24 breath/min and the minimum respiratory rate was observed in group-A, 6.20 ± 0.58 breath/min.

Table 4: Respiratory rate (breaths/min) of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	7	8	10	11	8	10
2	5	6	11	10	10	11
3	6	7	10	8	11	10
4	5	6	9	7	5	11
5	8	9	8	9	6	10
6	7	8	10	11	8	10
7	5	6	11	10	10	11
8	6	7	10	8	11	10
9	5	6	9	7	5	11
10	8	9	8	9	6	10
Mean ± SE	6.20 ±0.58e	7.20 ±0.58d	9.60 ±0.50b	9.00 ±0.70b	8.00 ±1.14c	10.40 ±0.24a

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between them

RBC ($\times 10^6$ /uL) count of Lassi Camel

Table 5 indicates that maximum value of RBC count was recorded in Group-F, $10.40 \pm 0.24 \times 10^6$ /uL and the minimum RBC count was observed in group-A, $6.80 \pm 0.37 \times 10^6$ /uL

Table 5: RBC ($\times 10^6$ /uL) count of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	7	8	9	10	11	10
2	6	7	10	10	10	11
3	8	9	9	11	11	10
4	7	8	10	10	10	11
5	6	7	9	9	9	10
6	7	8	9	10	11	10
7	6	7	10	10	10	11
8	8	9	9	11	11	10
9	7	8	10	10	10	11
10	6	7	9	9	9	10
Mean \pm SE	6.80 \pm0.37d	7.80 \pm0.37c	9.40 \pm0.24b	10.00 \pm0.31ab	10.20 \pm0.37a	10.40 \pm0.24a

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between them

PCV (%) of Lassi camel

Table 6 shows that maximum value of PCV percentage was recorded in Group-F, $43.60 \pm 0.33\%$ and the minimum PCV percentage was observed in group-A, $32.40 \pm 1.12\%$

Table 6: Packed Cell Volume (%) of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	39	30	34	37	41	44
2	30	32	36	38	40	42
3	30	34	37	30	41	43
4	31	36	35	37	43	45
5	32	38	36	38	42	44
6	39	30	34	37	41	44
7	30	32	36	38	40	42
8	30	34	37	30	41	43
9	31	36	35	37	43	45
10	32	38	36	38	42	44
Mean \pm SE	32.40 \pm1.12e	34.00 \pm0.94d	35.60 \pm0.33cd	36.00 \pm1.01c	41.40 \pm0.33b	43.60 \pm0.33a

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between them

Hemoglobin (g/dl) of Lassi Camel

Table 7 shows that maximum value of hemoglobin volume was recorded in Group-F, 15.40±0.40 g/dl and the minimum hemoglobin volume was observed in group-A, 11.20±0.37 g/dl.

Table 7: Hemoglobin (g/dl) of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	11	12	13	14	14	14
2	12	13	14	14	16	16
3	11	12	14	13	15	16
4	10	11	12	13	14	15
5	12	13	13	14	15	16
6	11	12	13	14	14	14
7	12	13	14	14	16	16
8	11	12	14	13	15	16
9	10	11	12	13	14	15
10	12	13	13	14	15	16
Mean ± SE	11.20 ±0.37c	12.20 ±0.37bc	13.20 ±0.37b	13.60 ±0.24b	14.80 ±0.37ab	15.40 ±0.40a

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant (p<0.05) difference between them

MCV (fL) of Lassi Camel

Table 8 shows that maximum value of MCV volume was recorded in group F, 34.00±0.89 fL and the minimum MCV volume was observed in group-A, 26.20±0.37 fL.

Table 8: MCV (fL) of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	27	28	29	30	32	33
2	26	29	31	31	32	33
3	27	28	29	32	31	32
4	26	27	30	33	34	35
5	25	28	31	35	36	37
6	27	28	29	30	32	33
7	26	29	31	31	32	33
8	27	28	29	32	31	32
9	26	27	30	33	34	35
10	25	28	31	35	36	37
Mean ± SE	26.20 ±0.37e	28.00 ±0.31d	30.00 ±0.44c	32.20 ±0.86bc	33.00 ±0.89b	34.00 ±0.89a

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant (p<0.05) difference between them

MCH (fL) of Lassi camel

Table 9 shows that maximum value of MCH volume was recorded in Group-F, 32.31±0.60 fL and the minimum MCH volume was observed in group-A, 17.00±0.14 fL.

Table 9: MCH (fL) of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	17.5	21.6	19.5	24.8	28.5	30.1
2	17.3	19.4	19.4	24.6	28.5	30.5
3	16.8	20.5	21.3	24.5	28.1	30.8
4	16.6	21.1	23.5	24.3	28.5	31.5
5	17.4	19.8	23.8	23.5	28.3	31.8
6	16.5	18.2	23.5	24.1	28.5	32.2
7	17.3	19.6	23.4	24.5	28.5	32.6
8	16.6	20.5	23.4	23.5	28.1	32.5
9	17.6	21.3	23.5	24.8	28.5	35.8
10	16.4	20.8	24.8	23.5	28.3	35.3
Mean ± SE	17.00 ±0.14f	20.28 ±0.32e	22.61 ±0.59d	24.21 ±0.16c	28.38 ±0.05b	32.31 ±0.60a

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant (p<0.05) difference between them

MCHC (g/dl) of Lassi camel

Table 10 shows that maximum value of MCHC volume was recorded in Group-F, 49.60±0.50 g/dl and the minimum MCHC volume was observed in group-A, 43.40±0.92 g/dl.

Table 10: MCHC (g/dl) of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	42	44	46	47	48	52
2	41	46	47	48	49	51
3	43	43	48	49	49	53
4	45	45	50	51	50	49
5	46	48	48	49	53	52
6	42	44	46	47	48	53
7	41	46	47	48	49	51
8	43	43	48	49	49	52
9	45	45	50	51	50	49
10	46	48	48	49	53	53
Mean ± SE	43.40 ±0.92f	45.20 ±0.86e	47.80 ±0.66d	48.80 ±0.66c	49.80 ±0.86b	51.50 ±0.47a

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant (p<0.05) difference between them

Neutrophils ($\times 10^3$ uL) count of camel

Table 11 shows that maximum value of neutrophils count was recorded in Group-F, $36.10 \pm 0.37 \times 10^3$ uL and the minimum neutrophils count was observed in group-A, $27.90 \pm 0.23 \times 10^3$ uL.

Table 11: Neutrophils ($\times 10^3$ uL) count of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	28	28	32	33	36	37
2	27	32	34	36	38	36
3	28	31	35	38	34	35
4	29	29	32	35	32	37
5	28	28	30	36	34	36
6	27	28	32	34	36	38
7	28	30	34	36	38	37
8	27	32	35	38	36	35
9	29	29	35	35	32	34
10	28	28	30	32	34	36
Mean \pm SE	27.90 $\pm 0.23f$	29.50 $\pm 0.52e$	32.90 $\pm 0.62d$	35.30 $\pm 0.61c$	35.00 $\pm 0.68b$	36.10 $\pm 0.37a$

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between them

Eosinophils ($\times 10^3$ uL) count of LAssi Camel

Table 12 shows that maximum value of eosinophils count was recorded in Group-F, $8.38 \pm 0.07 \times 10^3$ uL and the minimum eosinophils count was observed in group-A, $6.14 \pm 0.01 \times 10^3$ uL.

Table 12: Eosinophils ($\times 10^3$ uL) count of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	6.1	6.4	7.6	7.8	8.3	8.4
2	6.2	6.3	7.8	7.3	8.2	8.2
3	6.1	6.5	7.3	7.3	8.5	8.1
4	6.2	6.1	7.9	7.2	8.4	8.3
5	6.1	6.3	7.3	7.3	8.3	8.8
6	6.1	6.2	7.6	7.8	8.4	8.4
7	6.2	6.5	7.8	7.3	8.2	8.1
8	6.1	6.2	7.3	7.5	8.5	8.4
9	6.2	6.1	7.9	7.2	8.4	8.3
10	6.1	6.4	7.3	7.3	8.3	8.8
Mean \pm SE	6.14 $\pm 0.01c$	6.30 $\pm 0.04c$	7.58 $\pm 0.08b$	7.40 $\pm 0.07b$	8.35 $\pm 0.03a$	8.38 $\pm 0.07a$

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between them

Basophils ($\times 10^3$ uL) count of Lassi Camel

Table 13 shows that maximum value of basophils count was recorded in Group-F, $1.52 \pm 0.09 \times 10^3$ uL and the minimum basophils count was observed in group-A, $1.16 \pm 0.06 \times 10^3$ uL

Table 13: Basophils ($\times 10^3$ uL) count of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	1	1.1	1.5	1.9	1.8	1.4
2	1.5	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.9	1.9
3	1	1.1	1.5	1.1	1.3	1.2
4	1	1.4	1.4	1.1	1.3	1.3
5	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.8
6	1	1.1	1.5	1.9	1.3	1.4
7	1.5	1.2	1.2	1.4	1.1	1.9
8	1	1.1	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.2
9	1	1.4	1.2	1.1	1.5	1.3
10	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.8	1.8
Mean \pm SE	1.16 $\pm 0.06b$	1.22 $\pm 0.03b$	1.37 $\pm 0.04ab$	1.39 $\pm 0.09ab$	1.46 $\pm 0.08ab$	1.52 $\pm 0.09a$

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between them

Lymphocytes ($\times 10^3$ uL) count of Lassi camel

Table 14 shows that maximum value of lymphocytes count was recorded in Group-F, $53.10 \pm 0.45 \times 10^3$ uL and the minimum lymphocytes count was observed in group-A, $43.40 \pm 0.40 \times 10^3$ uL.

Table 14: Lymphocytes ($\times 10^3$ uL) of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	42	44	46	46	52	54
2	44	46	47	48	51	52
3	45	46	48	50	50	54
4	44	45	46	51	54	53
5	42	43	45	52	52	52
6	42	44	48	50	50	56
7	44	46	47	53	52	51
8	45	46	49	52	50	54
9	44	45	46	49	54	53
10	42	43	45	48	51	52
Mean \pm SE	43.40 $\pm 0.40f$	44.80 $\pm 0.38e$	46.70 $\pm 0.42d$	49.90 $\pm 0.69c$	51.60 $\pm 0.47b$	53.10 $\pm 0.45a$

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between them

Monocytes ($\times 10^3$ uL) count of Lassi camel

Table 15 shows maximum value of monocytes count was recorded in Group-F, $7.34 \pm 0.07 \times 10^3$ uL and the minimum monocytes count was observed in group-A, $5.32 \pm 0.05 \times 10^3$ uL

Table 15: Monocytes ($\times 10^3$ uL) of Lassi camel

Animal	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F
	3-24 months male	3-24 month's female	25-48 months' male	25-48 months female	60-72 months male	60-72 months female
1	5.3	5.6	6.3	6.5	7.3	7.6
2	5.2	5.5	6.3	6.1	7.2	7.2
3	5.1	5.2	6.2	6.6	7.1	7.1
4	5.6	5.9	6.1	6.8	7.3	7.6
5	5.4	5.6	6.5	6.6	7.2	7.2
6	5.3	5.6	6.3	6.5	7.3	7.6
7	5.2	5.5	6.2	6.1	7.2	7.2
8	5.1	5.2	6.0	6.6	7.1	7.1
9	5.6	5.9	6.1	6.8	7.3	7.6
10	5.4	5.6	6.5	6.6	7.2	7.2
Mean ± SE	5.32 ±0.05c	5.56 ±0.07c	6.25 ±0.05b	6.52 ±0.07b	7.22 ±0.02a	7.34 ±0.07a

Different alphabets among the mean values showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between them

DISCUSSIONS

The camel is a unique biological model and promising livestock in the climate-change context. Pakistan is one of the hotspot regions severely hit by the calamities of climate-change. The camel is the option hope and future food security livestock for the drought-stricken regions of the country, especially Thal, Cholistan and Thar Deserts. The studies of blood indices provide ample clue about health status and well-being of an animal so these can be used for evaluating the health condition of animal generally. It could be an interesting tool for monitoring the bill of health in camels (39). Observation of a deviation of certain blood parameters from their normal limits could be a guide for differential diagnosis of diseases. Despite of this fact, a few reports have been published on its blood parameters as affected by some physiological and pathological conditions or on the normal levels of blood constituents of camel calves and adults with regard of their age and physiological (40).

Findings of present study showed that numerically higher values for most of the physiological and hematological indices were determined in adult Lassi

camel aged 60-72 months' male than other age groups. Lower values for blood parameters were observed in Lassi foal camel aged 3-24 months' male. The results of current study are in accordance with (39) provided a comprehensive biochemical analysis of the major constituents of camels. All the blood parameters found higher in young camel than adult and suckling camels. All the values were found to be in normal range and the difference with other reported values may be attributed to breed, age, nutrition, husbandry conditions, environment and methods of the assay. Findings of (16) reported that the Hb, PCV, RBC, MCV, MCH and MCHC were lowest in young camels (3-12 weeks old). Similarly, (40) stated that significant variation for white blood cell counts, red blood cell counts, haemoglobin, packed cell volume and mean corpuscular haemoglobin was observed for males with age, while difference in white blood cell counts, red blood cell counts, haemoglobin, packed cell volume and mean corpuscular volume was observed for females. Moreover, (40) results obtained indicate that RBC, Hb and PCV decreased in the later stages of pregnancy while TLC remained unchanged.

Calculated indices revealed a significant increase in MCV ($p < 0.02$) of pregnant camels. (41) Reported average range values for haemoglobin as 11.5 g/dl. He also determined haematological status of camel calves of Sudan and stated higher haemoglobin concentration in suckling-calves as compared to lactating-dams. The results are consistent with the previous research (16), which found that the blood index increased with camel age. In Saudi Arabia, young Magaheim camels (3-4 months old) had a lower level of Hb (42), although the level was below the reference value. However, in India's single humped camel, Hb and complete erythrocyte count profile were found at greater levels (43). According to our study, (42) observed similar monocyte counts. Lymphocytes, followed by neutrophils, monocytes, eosinophils and basophils, are the most abundant white blood cells in camels (16). Eosinophil and neutrophil were found to rise, then decrease in pregnant camel lymphocytes and monocytes (44). In young Magaheim camels aged 3-4 months from Saudi Arabia, Neutrophil was the predominant white blood cell (42). The number of monocytes increased during the rainy season, while the number of lymphocytes, eosinophils and basophils increased during the humid rainy summer season (45).

CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded from present study that numerically higher values for most of the physiological and hematological indices were determined in Lassi adult male camel aged 60-72 months than other age groups. Lower values for blood parameters were observed in Lassi foal male camel aged 3-24 months. There was significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in all hematological parameters between the age groups.

Author's contribution

Conceptualization: IUK, UA

Methodology: JK, HS

Formal analysis: TA, SK, LK, SUR

Writing review and editing: IK, ARAK

All authors have read and agreed to the published version

Conflict of Interest

All authors declare no conflict of interest

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